

CRISPR/Cas-mediated heritable chromosome fusions in *Arabidopsis*

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Abstract: The genome of *Arabidopsis thaliana* consists of 10 chromosomes. By inducing CRISPR/Cas-mediated breaks at subcentromeric and subtelomeric sequences, we fused entire chromosome arms, obtaining two eight-chromosome lines. In one line, both arms of chromosome 3 were fused to chromosome 1. In another line, the arms were transferred to chromosomes 1 and 5. Both chromosome number-reduced lines are fertile. Phenotypic and transcriptional analyses revealed no differences compared to wild-type plants. After crossing with wild-type, the progeny shows reduced fertility. The meiotic recombination patterns of the transferred chromosome arms were drastically changed. Directed chromosome number changes in plants may enable new breeding strategies, redefining linkage groups and establishing genetic barriers. Moreover, our data indicate that plants are highly robust to engineered karyotype changes.

Main Text:

The emergence of the clustered regularly interspaced short palindromic repeats (CRISPR)/CRISPR-associated protein (Cas) system has allowed scientists to induce doublestrand breaks (DSBs) at almost any pre-defined position in the genome (1). In plants, this technique can be used for crop improvement by manipulating agronomically-important traits (2–4). However, besides gene modifications, larger structural changes can also be induced. Using the CRISPR/Cas-based chromosome engineering technique, large chromosomal rearrangements, such as inversions, can be induced in plants (5–10). Inversions are known to

modulate the recombination landscape along a chromosome by suppressing crossovers (COs) in the rearranged area (11–16). We could show the potential of inducing inversions for changing recombination patterns by both restoring CO rates in a previously CO-dead region (6) as well as excluding a substantial part of the Arabidopsis genome from meiotic recombination by inverting almost an entire chromosome (10).

Besides inversions, chromosome fusions are also implicated in speciation via reproductive isolation due to the production of inviable gametes (17). As a proof-of-concept, we aimed to artificially reduce chromosome numbers by inducing chromosome fusions. Thus far, chromosome number changes have been achieved in a targeted manner in only a few other nonplant organisms (18–20).

Our results demonstrate the resilience of the plant genome towards massive restructuring, while our approach provides a unique opportunity for gaining further insights into speciation, genome evolution and potential biotechnological applications.

Creation of the 8-chromosome lines

Our approach required the introduction of two consecutively induced chromosome (arm) fusions in the form of reciprocal translocations between both arms of chromosome 3 and the ends of one or two receiving chromosomes. To obtain these rare events, we used our protocol for inducing Mb-sized chromosomal rearrangements in Arabidopsis (21). As genetic background, either the WT Col-0 (for line F8) or the *ku70* mutant (for line T8) were used. The *ku70* mutant was chosen because we had observed increased rearrangement frequencies in this line compared to WT in previous experiments, due to the absence of the classical nonhomologous end joining (NHEJ) DSB repair pathway (5, 22). To ensure the production of heritable events, we combined the *Staphylococcus aureus* orthologue of Cas9 and the *Lachnospiraceae bacterium* variants ttLbCas12a or ttLbCas12a-I (23, 24), optimized for plant use, with an egg cell-specific promoter (25). Using this setup, two DSBs were induced at the borders of the core centromere of chromosome 3 as well as near the telomere repeats of the respective receiver chromosomes (Table S1). To create line F8 (Fig. 1a), the short arm of chromosome 3 was first transferred onto the long arm of chromosome 1, creating a telocentric and elongated chromosome. In the second step, the remaining arm of the telocentric chromosome was transferred onto the short arm of chromosome 1, resulting in one very large fusion chromosome. Line T8 (Fig. 1b) was generated by first transferring the short arm of chromosome 3 onto the long arm of chromosome 5, and then transferring the remaining arm of chromosome 3 from the telocentric chromosome onto the long arm of chromosome 1 in the second step, generating two elongated fusion chromosomes in the process. As a by-product of these approaches, the generation of a mini-chromosome was expected, consisting of the functional centromere of chromosome 3 and two short (~ 10 kb) telomere ends of either chromosome 1 (line F8) or chromosomes 1 and 5 (line T8), respectively. However, due to its small size as well as its lack of essential genetic information (see Table S2), we expected it might get lost in the progeny due to segregation problems.

We first screened for plants where the short arm of chromosome 3 was either translocated onto the end of the long arm of chromosome 1 (line F8) or 5 (line T8). One plant of line T8 and two

plants of line F8 were found to carry the translocation heterozygously (Table S3; Table S4). The recombinant T8 plant and one of the two positively identified F8 plants were chosen for further experiments and establishment of homozygosity. Homozygous plants were then subjected to a second round of chromosome engineering to transfer the remaining long arm of chromosome 3 onto the short arm (line F8) or long arm (line T8) of chromosome 1. For line F8, five lines were found to carry independent arm transfers (see Tables S3 and S4). When screening line T8 for the second arm transfer, four lines with independent arm transfer events were identified (see

Figure 1. Schematic overview of the generation of the two 8-chromosome lines F8 and T8. Schematic overview of the induced chromosome arm translocations of chromosome 3 in lines F8 and T8, leading to the creation of a 8-chromosome karyotype. As a by-product, the generation of a minichromosome was expected, consisting of the functional centromere of chromosome 3 and two short (~ 10 kb) telomere ends of chromosome 1 or chromosomes 1 and 5. However, due to its small size as well as its lack of essential genetic information, we expected it might get lost in the progeny. Red triangles and dashed lines indicate the location of CRISPR/Cas-induced DSBs. (A) Schematic overview of the induced chromosome arm translocations of chromosome 3 in line F8. First, two DSBs were induced at the border of the core centromere of chromosome 3 as well as near the telomere sequences of chromosome 1. This resulted in the transfer of the short arm of chromosome 3 onto the long arm of chromosome 1, creating a telocentric and elongated chromosome via a reciprocal translocation in the process. Next, two DSBs were induced at the border of the core centromere of chromosome 3 on the remaining arm, as well as near the remaining telomere sequences of chromosome 1. This resulted in the transfer of the remaining long arm of chromosome 3 onto the short arm of chromosome 1, creating a

fusion chromosome of chromosomes 1 and 3. **(B)** Schematic overview of the induced chromosome arm translocations of chromosome 3 in line T8. First, two DSBs were induced at the border of the core centromere of chromosome 3 as well as near the telomere sequences of chromosome 5. This resulted in the transfer of the short arm of chromosome 3 onto the long arm of chromosome 5, creating a telocentric and elongated chromosome via a reciprocal translocation in the process. Next, two DSBs were induced at the border of the core centromere of chromosome 3 on the remaining arm, as well as near the telomere sequences of chromosome 1. This resulted in the transfer of the remaining long arm of chromosome 3 onto the long arm of chromosome 1 in inverted orientation, creating another elongated chromosome in the process.

Tables S3 and S4). In two of these lines, Mendelian segregation of the arm transfer junction was detected, yielding homozygous 8-chromosome lines in the T2 generation. In line F8, but not line T8, a junction indicative of the presence of the minichromosome (in the heterozygous state) could be detected, and in only one of three minichromosome-positive lines, the minichromosome was inherited. By screening three different seed batches of this line, the minichromosome junction could be detected in 8, 10 or 14 out of 80 screened plants, respectively. This indicates that the minichromosome is rapidly lost during propagation as it apparently does not contain any essential genetic information (see Table S2). To establish lines F8 and T8, one minichromosome-negative line each was chosen for further experiments and homozygous mutants propagated. All newly formed translocation junctions that were amplified by PCR and analyzed by Sanger sequencing exhibited InDels around the ligation sites (Fig. S1). In line T8 (*ku70* genetic background), deletion repair patterns, likely resulting from microhomology-mediated end joining repair, could be observed. Furthermore, the translocation and fusion events generated in both 8-chromosome lines were validated by FISH using chromosomal segment-specific probes (Fig. 2a-d; Table S5). The loss of the centromeric minichromosomes, formed from chromosome 3, and the reduction of the chromosome numbers to 8 were confirmed in both lines by 4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole (DAPI) staining of mitotic chromosomes (Fig. 2e) and immunostaining of interphase nuclei with a centromere-specific CENH3 antibody (Fig. 2f). A maximum of 8 CENH3 signals were detected in both engineered lines in contrast the majority of nuclei showed up to 10 signals in WT Col-0 nuclei (Fig. 2f). To further confirm the genomic structure and to rule out the occurrence of major off-target rearrangements, both homozygous 8-chromosome lines were sequenced using the PacBio HiFi sequencing method. The expected junctions were verified, and no major off-target chromosomal rearrangements were detected (Figs. S2-S3; Data S1).

Gene expression and phenotype remain unaffected by the karyotype changes

Next, the effect of the chromosome fusions on gene expression was determined. Compared to WT Col-0, only 0.3% (88 genes) and 0.5% (151 genes) of total genes (27,000) in line F8 and line T8, respectively, displayed significant differential expression (Fig. S4). In both lines, the differentially expressed genes (DEGs) were distributed over the entire genome and there was little overlap between them (Fig. S4). The GO term analysis of the DEGs mostly showed their enrichment in metabolism pathways and no association with DNA repair mechanisms (Fig. S5). The identified DEGs were not located near the chromosomal fusion sites, ruling out a chromosome position effect on gene expression.

In addition, the macroscopic effects of the chromosome number reductions were analyzed in lines T8 and F8. Phenotypes were monitored across multiple developmental stages; from late seedlings up to 22 days-after-sowing (DAS), with a total of 7 scanning sessions (Figure S6a). The PlantScreen system measured 10 morphological parameters, ranging from basic traits, such as a raw area or perimeter, to more complex ones, e.g., compactness or slenderness of leaves (26). Phenotypic data from each scan were analyzed by principal component analysis (PCA; Fig. S7; Data S2). To enable an integrated comparison of developmental phenotypes, the PCA was performed across all time points (Fig. 3a, Data S2). The first two principal components (PC1, PC2) explained 71.4% and 17.4% of the total variation, respectively. For a more comprehensive view of phenotypic variation, PCA results were visualized in 3D by including PC3, which accounted for 5.8% of the total variation (Fig. S8; Data S2). Next, root morphology was assessed by measuring the primary root length of seedlings (Fig. S6b, Data S2), revealing no significant differences between the engineered and Col-0 lines. Seed phenotyping analysis further confirmed these results (Fig. S9, Data S2). These data clearly demonstrate that the 8-chromosome plants retained a WT-like phenotype throughout all developmental phases.

Figure 2. Confirmation of the 8-chromosome lines by FISH, DAPI staining and CENH3 immunostaining. (A) Schematic overview showing placement of the FISH probe combinations in WT

Col-0 (left) and line F8 (right). Red triangles and dashed lines indicate the location of CRISPR/Cas-induced DSBs. The positions of FISH probes are indicated by colored circles. **(B)** FISH of mitotic Col-0 and F8 chromosomes with the probe combination of yellow, dark blue and magenta (Table S5). On Col-0 chromosomes, blue and magenta signals are located on chromosome 3 and the yellow signal is located on chromosome 1; in line F8, blue and magenta signals colocalize with yellow on the same fusion chromosome. Chromatin was counterstained with DAPI (in grey). Scale bar = 10 μ m. **(C)** Schematic overview showing placement of the FISH probe combinations in Col-0 (left), intermediate line T10, harboring the first chromosome arm translocation (middle), and line T8 (right). **(D)** FISH of mitotic Col-0, T10 and T8 mitotic chromosomes. In Col-0 (*), the probe combination magenta and green (Table S5) is located on separate chromosomes 3 and 5, while in line T10, colocalization of the probes confirms the first translocation event between chromosomes 3 and 5. In Col-0 (**), the probe combination yellow and dark blue (Table S5) is located on separate chromosomes 1 and the remaining arm of chromosome 3, while in line T8, colocalization of the probes confirms the second chromosome arm transfer. Chromatin was counterstained with DAPI (in grey). Scale bar = 10 μ m. **(E)** DAPIstained mitotic chromosomes of lines F8, T8 and Col-0. Scale bar = 10 μ m. **(F)** Anti-CENH3 labelled interphase nuclei of lines F8 and T8 as well as Col-0. The rare occurrence of nuclei with CENH3 signals above 10 is explained by the partial separation of sister chromatids (43). Per line, at least 30 nuclei were analyzed.

Fertility of the eight-chromosome lines.

We assessed the effect of the chromosome fusions on the fertility of homozygous and heterozygous mutant plants compared to WT Col-0 plants by counting the number of seeds per silique. In both lines, the total seed number did not differ significantly between homozygous mutant and WT plants, thus haploid gametes of both 8-chromosome karyotypes seem to be fully fertile (Fig. 3b,c, Data S2). In the case of line F8 (Fig. 3b), we detected a decrease in the seed number per silique by about 60% in heterozygous plants compared with WT plants and the homozygous mutant. In the case of line T8, the seed number of heterozygous plants was reduced by three quarters compared with WT plants and the homozygous mutant (Fig. 3c). We speculated that meiotic pairing defects of the fusion chromosome with Arabidopsis WT chromosomes might lead to partial infertility. In the case line F8, both WT chromosomes 3 and 1 must pair simultaneously with the fused chromosome to enable proper segregation and, thus, viable gametes. To visualize the meiotic behaviour of line F8, DAPI staining was performed on meiotic metaphase I chromosome spreads prepared from the hybrid plants between line F8 and WT. As expected, we detected three bivalents and one trivalent. In contrast, WT plants showed the formation of five bivalents (Fig. 3d-f).

Figure 3. Phenotypic and fertility analyses of lines F8 and T8 and meiotic chromosome pairing behavior of the 8-chromosome line F8. (A) PCA plot (left) and bi-plot (right) integrating phenotypic data of all seven scanned developmental stages. Arrows indicate the contribution of the individual morphological traits to the principal components (the longer the arrow, the higher the contribution). For each phenotype scan, $n \geq 30$ independent biological replicates for F8 and T8 and $n \geq 15$ for Col-0. For a more comprehensive

view of phenotypic variation, PCA results were visualized in 3D by including PC3, which accounted for 5.8% of the total variation (see Fig. S8). **(B-C)** Nine or ten homozygous, heterozygous, and Col-0 WT (Col) plants were randomly selected for fertility analysis ($n = 9$ or 10). Ten siliques per plant were randomly selected, and the number of seeds per silique was counted. The data were normalized to the mean seed count of Col-0, which was set to 100%. The boxplot shows the 9 or 10 independent biological replicates for each genotype. The middle line represents the median, box edges represent the first and third quartiles, and whiskers extend to the minimum and maximum values. Individual data points are represented as open circles. The median values are indicated next to the middle line of each boxplot. P values were calculated using a two-sided Mann-Whitney U Test ($***P < 0.001$; NS, not significant). **(B)** Fertility analysis of homozygous and heterozygous plants of line F8 as well as WT Col-0 plants. The seed number of the heterozygous plants was significantly reduced, by 56 and 61%, compared with Col-0 and homozygous plants, respectively. The seed number of homozygous and Col-0 plants did not differ significantly. **(C)** Fertility analysis of homozygous and heterozygous plants of line T8 as well as WT Col-0 plants. The seed number of the heterozygous plants was significantly reduced, by 76%, compared with Col-0 and homozygous plants. The seed number of homozygous and Col-0 plants did not differ significantly. **(D-E)** Meiotic chromosome pairing behavior of hybrids of the 8-chromosome line F8 and Col-0 **(D)** as well as Col-0 plants **(E)**. The F8 x Col-0 hybrid shows the formation of one trivalent (marked by t) plus three bivalents (marked by b). **(E)** The metaphase I cell of Col-0 shows five bivalents. Chromatin was counterstained with DAPI (in grey). Scale bar = 10 μm . **(F)** Scheme of the formation of 1 trivalent plus 3 bivalents in the F8 x Col-0 hybrid plant.

Chromosome fusions change recombination patterns in hybrids

To elucidate how the chromosome fusions influence meiotic recombination in hybrids, both homozygous engineered 8-chromosome lines were crossed with the *A. thaliana* ecotype Landsberg erecta (Ler-1), harbouring the WT 10-chromosome set. Subsequently, F1 seeds were harvested and propagated to obtain F2 seeds. The recombination frequency was determined by analysing 400 plants per line that were grown from the F2 seeds. As a control, 400 plants of the progeny of crosses between WT Col-0 and Ler-1 (control for line F8) or *ku70* and Ler-1 (control for line T8), respectively, were analyzed. Using a TaqMan single-nucleotide polymorphism (SNP) genotyping assay, we selected SNP markers approximately every 2 Mb on the fused chromosomes to detect marker changes between Col-0 and Ler-1 alleles (see Table S4 and S6). First, the presence or absence of a marker change was analyzed in each sample in each marker interval. Then, based on the total number of marker changes in each marker interval, the recombination frequency was determined (Fig. 4, Data S2). In both lines, the chromosome fusion sites were depleted of COs compared to the respective chromosome areas in the control. At the same time, the recombination pattern detected in all translocated arms of chromosome 3 was inverted, shifting the COs from the fusion sites towards the telomeric ends. On the other hand, the recombination pattern in the respective fusion partners, chromosome 1 or chromosome 5, was either unchanged or only slightly different from that in the corresponding WT control. Also, in the long arm of chromosome 4, which was analyzed as another control, no difference was observed between the engineered lines and the WT regarding the recombination pattern. Thus, the chromosome arm transfers influenced the recombination landscape specifically at the fusion sites and in the fused arms.

Figure 4. Recombination frequency on the fusion chromosome arms and long arm of chromosome 4. (A) The recombination frequency on the fusion chromosome 1/3 (top) and long arm of chromosome 4 (bottom) as a control in line F8 was determined by SNP-based genotyping of 400 plants (independent biological replicates) of the offspring of the F8 x Ler-1 line and the Col-0 x Ler-1 control. The recombination frequency is presented in cM/Mb. Chromosomal areas that were not analyzed are greyed out. (B) The recombination frequency on the arms of the fusion chromosome 1/3 (left) and 5/3 (right) as well as the long arm of chromosome 4 (bottom) as a control in line T8 was determined by SNP-based genotyping of 400 plants (independent biological replicates) of the offspring of the T8 x Ler-1 line and the *ku70* x Ler-1 control. The recombination frequency is presented in cM/Mb. Chromosomal areas that were not analyzed are greyed out. In both lines, we detected an inverted recombination pattern in the

two translocated arms of chromosome 3, shifting the CO from the fusion sites towards the telomeric ends. At the same time, the chromosome fusion sites were depleted of COs compared to the respective chromosome areas in the control. The recombination pattern in the fusion partners, chromosome 1 and/or 5, did not differ from the pattern in the control.

Discussion

With the advance of large-scale sequencing and chromosome painting technologies, it became clear that chromosome fusion events regularly take place in the course of genome evolution (27–29). The development of the CRISPR/Cas-mediated chromosome engineering technology has now allowed us to fuse chromosomes in a pre-defined way and, thus, to induce the first chromosome number reductions in plants in a targeted manner. Remarkably, the 8-chromosome *Arabidopsis* lines exhibited a completely WT-like phenotype during development and only minimal transcriptomic changes (30). Furthermore, the identified DEGs were not involved in DNA repair, indicating regular genome stability as no persistent DNA damage signalling takes place in these lines (31). These results also strongly resemble those we obtained when analysing two 5 and 7.5 Mb-sized CRISPR/Cas-induced chromosomal inversions (7) and 0.5 Mb translocations (30) regarding their effect on epigenetic landscape and gene expression. Taken together, all of these recent results demonstrate the robustness of the plant genome towards substantial chromosomal restructuring.

However, chromosome fusions may have dramatic consequences for the evolution of species as they often go hand in hand with reduced fertility in hybrids. Crossing with WT karyotypes results in heterozygotes which, due to disturbed meiotic pairing of the homologous chromosomes, display the generation of imbalanced gametes (17). In our study, we found a reduction in fertility of about 60% in line F8 and three quarters in line T8 compared to WT plants, respectively. We anticipate that with further structural chromosome changes, reproductive isolation between engineered and WT *Arabidopsis* plants will be achievable. In addition, using such a strategy, it should be possible to contain crops genetically and prevent outcrossing with wild relatives.

In haploid yeast, drastic chromosome number reductions were achieved by inducing consecutive chromosome fusions, leading to a reduction of the chromosome number from 16 to one and two chromosomes, respectively (18, 19). On the other hand, the first chromosome fusions in mammals was achieved by editing haploid embryonic mice stem cells, resulting in the generation of animals with 19 instead of 20 pairs of chromosomes by fusing the two largest mouse chromosomes 1 and 2 as well as the two medium-sized chromosomes 4 and 5 (20). In all three studies, no major growth defects were detected, however in contrast to our study, varying degrees of fertility impairments were observed.

In our experiments, the observed reduced fertility in heterozygotes indicates that meiotic segregation was affected by the presence of the chromosome fusions. As successful chromosome pairing is a prerequisite for balanced segregation of the haploid chromosome sets during meiosis, aberrant gametes might have been produced due to the mis-segregation of the non-aligned engineered and WT chromosomes. One has to expect the formation of trivalents, a likely complex and error-prone process, in such a situation as the chromosomes with the fused arms of chromosome 3 are able to pair with two different WT chromosomes at the same time.

Indeed, we were able to identify such a structure during meiosis (Fig. 4c). Besides segregation, the natural recombination reaction itself might also have been influenced by the chromosome structure changes. Indeed, in the offspring of crosses between the engineered 8-chromosome lines and Ler-1 (with a 10-chromosome set), we did observe in both analyzed lines that the fusion sites were depleted of COs compared to the respective chromosome areas in the control, indicating impairments in homolog pairing close to the newly added heterologies. Notably, in both analyzed lines, the recombination pattern detected in all translocated arms of chromosome 3 was inverted, shifting the COs from the fusion sites towards the subtelomeric ends. Taken together, these results could indicate that the complete formation of the synaptonemal complex during meiosis, a prerequisite for CO formation (32), was inhibited close to the fusion sites. The observed increase in CO frequencies toward the chromosome ends could be due to a compensation mechanism, accounting for the reduced CO frequencies at the fusion sites to allow for the obligate CO necessary for proper segregation of the chromatids (32, 33). For plant breeders, it will be of particular interest that, by inducing large chromosomal translocations, the recombination landscape can be changed, both by reducing CO numbers near the newly brought-in heterologous regions and, at the same time, by enhancing COs in the subtelomeric parts of the elongated chromosome arms. Future application of the 8-chromosome lines in combination with meiotic mutants might be helpful to test the interplay between chromosome number reduction and interference-sensitive versus interference-insensitive CO pathways and to test the coarsening model (34).

The applied chromosome fusion approach can also help answer other basic research questions. For example, what are the minimum and maximum lengths of Arabidopsis chromosomes to be still inherited? Minichromosomes are often lost during meiosis (35). In our lines the minichromosomes were not carrying essential genes, so it is likely that there was no selective pressure to inherit them over several generations. However, we should soon be able to define the minimal size of functional Arabidopsis chromosomes by inducing translocations of different sizes (36). Generally, minichromosomes have considerable potential for breeding applications as they can be used as vectors for stacking and transferring many genes, such as genes associated with increased nutritional value, pest resistance or tolerance to abiotic stress (37). Since they segregate independently of the other native chromosomes, linkage drag can be avoided. For the same reason, CRISPR/Cas editing components could be placed on minichromosomes and later easily eliminated from the genome by back-crossing to achieve transgene-free lines (38).

On the other hand, an upper limit on chromosome size has been suggested by studying artificially increased chromosome arms in *Vicia faba* and barley (39, 40). Those studies indicated that the chromosome arms must not exceed half of the average length of the spindle axis at telophase to avoid truncation of the non-separated sister chromatids by the newly forming cell wall, causing a loss of genetic information. In our study, all obtained elongated chromosome arms still adhered to this proposed length limit. Future experiments using chromosome engineering could help to illuminate whether the proposed length limit can be confirmed in Arabidopsis, too.

Artificially induced chromosome fission has been achieved in plants (41, 42). A synthetic centromere was inserted into chromosome 4 of maize, making it a functional dicentric chromosome. Random chromosome breakage during segregation resulted in a line harbouring

a chromosome number of 22 instead of 20. The resulting plants showed no phenotypic deviation or growth defects and reproduced normally with 20-chromosome lines. By combining this approach with CRISPR/Cas-mediated chromosome engineering, one should be able to break up chromosomes at the desired position. In summary, our study demonstrates that by using CRISPR/Cas we can now change the karyotype of plants in a pre-defined way. CRISPR/Cas-mediated chromosome number changes should be applicable to crops despite their larger and more complex genomes. In our experiments in *Arabidopsis*, we obtained translocation frequencies of complete chromosome arms of about one out of a thousand tested plants (see Table S3). Because large intrachromosomal rearrangements have already been achieved in crops such as rice and maize (8, 9), at frequencies similar to those observed in *Arabidopsis* (6, 10), obtaining chromosome fusions in crops should not pose a significant obstacle, provided that efficient plant transformation and screening protocols are used. Applying directed karyotype engineering will also allow us to mimic evolution, explore chromosome length limits or achieve artificial reproductive isolation in the near future.

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